

RSS Gradient-Assisted Frontier Exploration and Radio Source Localization

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Abstract—We consider the combined problem of frontier exploration in a complex indoor environment while seeking a radio source. To do this in an efficient manner, we incorporate radio signal strength (RSS) information into the exploration algorithm by locally sampling the RSS and estimating the 2-D RSS gradient. The algorithm exploits the local motion to collect RSS samples for gradient estimation and seeks to explore in a way that brings the robot to the signal source. This strategy avoids random or exhaustive exploration. An indoor experiment demonstrates the exploration algorithm that uses this information to dynamically prioritize candidate frontiers and traverse to a radio source. Simulations, including radio propagation modeling with a ray-tracing algorithm, enable study of control algorithm tradeoffs and statistical performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are many problems in mobile robotics that require maintenance of reliable communication between robots or between robots and a base station including applications of sensor data collection or collaborative control. However, radio-based connectivity in a complex environment is severely challenged by the rapid fading or fluctuation of received radio signal strength (RSS) induced by multipath radio propagation.

Fading is characterized by dramatic RSS change over relatively small movements [1]. However, mobility can be exploited to improve RSS and therefore enhance connectivity in networked teams [2]. Although a complex environment results in significant spatial variation in the fading model parameters, the radio propagation environment can be characterized using a variety of fading models [3]. Another approach employed by Fink et al., in [4] presents a nonparametric method for RSS mapping using Gaussian processes where mobile agents learn a propagation model for the environment with a fixed radio source.

Instead of focusing on the task of learning propagation models, we couple the geometric exploration problem for an unknown environment with the additional objective of increasing RSS by reducing the distance to a radio source – e.g., an access point or sensor node. Accordingly, we assume that the robot can solve the simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) problem but does not know a radio propagation map a priori. We also assume that RSS measurements relative to a fixed radio source can only be performed onboard the robot.

In keeping with our goal of avoiding the radio propagation modeling problem, we rely on local *changes* to RSS and seek to estimate the two-dimensional gradient as in [5]. The RSS

gradient will provide information about the source direction provided sufficient average signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the receiver. The magnitude of the RSS gradient will also increase as the range to the source decreases.

Sun et al., considered a scenario exploiting the RSS gradient within a cooperating sensor network, to localize and navigate to a radio source [6]. Simulations were provided in an open environment, not accounting for RSS fluctuation due to small scale fading. Han et al., developed a triangulation algorithm to localize a stationary access point, by utilizing RSS gradients to estimate the angle of arrival to multiple cooperating platforms [7]. They provided outdoor experimental results and compared with other localization approaches. Wadhwa et al., considered an outdoor problem of exploiting RSS gradient to guide a UAV to a source on the ground. They developed an RSS spatial correlation model to optimize the RSS spatial sampling trajectory, and provided simulations [8]. Our approach differs in that we consider exploration in a complex indoor unknown environment with small scale fading.

In this paper, we extend the work of [5] and consider how the 2-D RSS gradient may be used in conjunction with frontier exploration to robustly guide a robot through a complex indoor environment to a radio signal source. Specifically, we seek to guide mobility in a way that brings the robot to the signal source in an efficient manner that avoids random or exhaustive exploration. In Section II we present our algorithm for RSS gradient-assisted exploration of an unknown environment. Section III details an experimental validation of this work on a ground platform with real RSS measurements and Section IV explores a number of Monte Carlo simulations that demonstrate the effect of various parameters on the performance of our approach. We conclude in Section V with some avenues for future work and summarizing remarks.

II. RSS GRADIENT-ASSISTED EXPLORATION

The RSS exploration algorithm consists of three phases. The Initial Exploration phase describes how the robot samples its immediate area at initialization. Afterwards, the Guided Exploration phase calculates the best next frontier to explore. This frontier is used as a navigation goal in the Navigation and Sampling phase. This algorithm balances geometric exploration of an unknown environment with a radio-source seeking behavior that drives the robot towards areas of increased SNR.

A. Initial Exploration

At initialization, the robot has no prior knowledge of the RSS environment, and thus has no directional preference for its movements. Instead, it begins by making RSS measurements as it explores the immediate area. After this initial exploration, it calculates the gradient of the RSS (Appendix I) to determine in which direction the signal strength is increasing the fastest. If the RSS gradient is sufficiently strong, the robot moves in the specified direction to exploit this knowledge; otherwise, the robot continues to explore the local area. In Appendix II, we discuss how to efficiently sample RSS for robust gradient estimates.

After it obtains a preliminary RSS gradient estimate, the robot alternates between *guided exploration* (selecting the best waypoint from the list of identified frontiers) and *navigation* (moving towards the current waypoint).

B. Guided Exploration

The robot identifies candidate frontiers on its map based on explored and unexplored regions. For each frontier, it calculates three metrics – RSS gradient, average RSS, and inverse distance. Afterwards, it selects the highest ranking frontier as its waypoint based on these three metrics.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the frontier exploration algorithm.

1) *Identify Frontiers*: A frontier is defined by cells in an occupancy-grid map that border known free-space and unknown regions. Frontier segments are identified by a k -means algorithm [9]. This algorithm calculates the centroids of clustered groups based on known boundary cells in the map. We assume that large groups of frontier points correspond to frontier segments that can be pursued during exploration. An example situation is presented in Fig. 2. In this figure, a robot has traversed a subset of the environment. It has cleared an area and identified the known boundary. By clustering with the k -means algorithm, several frontiers have been identified.

Fig. 2. Illustration of frontier identification for a particular configuration. Points on the boundary of known and unknown space are clustered to identify likely frontiers that can be explored.

2) *Calculate Metrics*: Once the set of frontiers is determined, the algorithm calculates three metrics: inverse distance from the current robot position, agreement with RSS gradient, and average RSS magnitude. Fig. 3 depicts an example scenario where these metrics are evaluated.

The inverse distance from the robot's current position to a frontier represents a greedy metric that can be used for exploration. By driving to the closest frontier, unknown space is explored with minimum cost. Conversely, this metric decreases the possibility that a distant frontier is explored without a reasonable expectation to increase the SNR.

The evaluation of RSS-based metrics requires that a subset of the collected RSS samples be associated with each candidate frontier. This association is computed according to the geodesic or path-distance rather than Euclidean distance such that the n closest samples are associated with each frontier. We assume that these samples will be spatially close. This close spacing allows us to approximate the RSS gradient with a plane. The approximated RSS gradient and average RSS magnitude is computed for each subset of RSS samples. The RSS gradient is the primary metric for controlling the robot towards the signal source. The gradient can be approximated given a set of well spaced points in a local area. However, there are certain cases where it is not possible to sample a set of well spaced points. In these cases the RSS average is useful for compensating for an uncertain gradient approximation. Intuitively, the RSS average does not require points to be well spaced but does require that

Fig. 3. Example of frontier ranking. Because frontiers 1 and 2 are closely located, they use the same n closest RSS measurements for calculating RSS gradient and average. Frontier 1 is ranked highest because, though inverse distance and RSS are similar to Frontier 2, its direction is closest to the gradient. Frontier 3 is ranked lowest because it is far away, disagrees with the gradient direction, and has the lowest RSS value.

different RSS averages be spaced far apart. In Section IV we perform a number of Monte Carlo simulations which show that using both metrics is better than just RSS gradient or RSS average.

3) *Select waypoint*: Through the execution of the frontier exploration algorithm, three different metrics are optimized. The three metrics are combined into a single objective function as a weighted sum. These weights were tuned after several simulation and experimental trials. The average RSS and gradient metrics allow source seeking for different sampling conditions. As a result, these metrics are similarly weighted. Increasing the weight of the inverse distance metric makes the algorithm favor an increasingly greedy exploration of the closest frontier. After the appropriate weights were determined they could be used for both the experimental and simulation trials. The sum of these weighted metrics gives us the ranking for each frontier. The highest-ranked frontier is chosen as the next waypoint for exploration.

C. Navigation and Sampling

In typical scenarios, the robot would take the shortest straight-line path to reach the selected frontier. However, this leads to unsuitable RSS gradient estimates because the sampling locations cannot be co-linear, as discussed in Appendix II. Therefore, rather than travel in straight-line trajectories, the robot introduces gentle oscillations to its path (see Fig. 4). This makes the gradient estimate more robust at the cost of greater distance traveled.

As the robot moves towards the current waypoint, it periodically updates its ranking of the set of frontiers based on newly acquired RSS samples. Because it is approaching the waypoint, it collects more accurate gradient data about that particular frontier. When the new RSS measurements corroborate the choice of waypoint (e.g., gradient points

Fig. 4. From left to right, the sampling strategies yield more RSS gradient confidence in the vertical direction at the expense of lower confidence in the horizontal direction. In each case, the distance between sequential sampling locations is identical.

towards waypoint, RSS average continues to increase), the robot will continue to the waypoint. A new frontier is selected if the ranking of the waypoint drops. Upon reaching the waypoint, if the SNR condition indicating sufficient proximity to the source has not been met, the robot will resume frontier exploration by identifying new frontiers from its current position.

If, in the course of movement towards a waypoint, the gradient becomes contradictory and/or the RSS drops, the robot is able to halt progress before reaching the waypoint and resume frontier exploration by identifying new frontiers from its current position. This capability is particularly useful to avoid exploring large rooms where exploration time can be significant. In order to avoid too many false alarms, we do not halt movement until the current waypoint drops a certain number of ranks in the overall list of candidate frontiers.

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

The robot used in the experiments is shown in Fig. 5. The *Scarab* is a small indoor ground platform equipped with a differential drive system, onboard computation, and 802.11a wireless communication in addition to its *Zigbee* radio which is used for experimental measurements. It is also equipped with a scanning laser range finder which is leveraged to yield accurate self-localization.

The robot has the ability to record RSSI (RSS indicator). This value is reported by the *Zigbee* radio whenever it receives a packet from the fixed source. To smooth the effects of channel noise, the robot averages the RSSI at locations within distance d of each other. We chose $d = 12.5\text{cm} = 1\lambda$ at 2.4 GHz, a distance that has been experimentally shown to result in approximately decorrelated fading [10]. Other testing parameters are shown in Table I.

Experimental implementation leads to some modifications to the algorithm described above. First, practical restrictions created arbitrary non-obstacle boundaries in the indoor testing environment. We use an a priori map on the *Scarab's* path planner in order to enforce these restrictions. The number of

Fig. 5. *Scarab* robot used in experiments. It is capable of self-localization and point-to-point radio signal strength measurements with an off-the-shelf *Zigbee* radio.

TABLE I
TABLE OF PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
number of frontiers (k)	12
closest RSS samples (n) (used to evaluate each frontier)	10
exploration radius	2.5 m
oscillation amplitude	0.375 m
independent sampling distance	0.125 m

frontiers to identify with the k-means clustering algorithm was set at $k = 12$ because some frontiers would inevitably be identified inside regions that were out of bounds. The large number of frontiers helped ensure the robot would be able to consider all frontiers as well as ones the robot is not permitted to explore.

In the experimental trial depicted in Figure 6, the *Scarab* starts at one end of the hallway. It randomly explores the local area until it makes a reliable RSS gradient estimate and is able to intelligently select a frontier for exploration. As it oscillates about a path between frontiers, the robot collects RSSI data. However, there are some areas where the robot is not able to receive a signal. In this particular experiment the robot starts exploring away from the source, but turns around after exploring its first frontier. Afterwards it moves up the hallway, past several offices and collects data near the room with the source. The robot detects the higher RSSI average and gradient pointing towards the source, and successfully explores the room containing the source. Once the average RSSI exceeds the SNR threshold, the robot has reached the desired vicinity of the source and stops.

The average RSSI is plotted in Fig. 7 over the path covered by the robot. We examine the behavior of the algorithm as the robot explores the environment. In epoch (A), the time until A in the figure, the robot observes weak RSSI while performing area exploration. The robot is able to extract gradient information to steer it down the hallway towards the source. In epoch (B), the robot observes steadily increasing gradient, thus corroborating the decision to move down the hallway. Note that although the average RSSI shows the

Fig. 6. Trajectory taken in an experimental trial with the *Scarab* mobile robot. Received signal strength at each point is indicated by the intensity. Physical locations (A)–(E) correspond to the points labeled in Fig. 7

Fig. 7. Received signal strength during the experimental trial depicted in Fig. 6. Note that RSS is variable over small distances but generally increases throughout the trial.

effect of strong fading, the gradient estimate is able to detect the gradual trend of the RSSI. The robot nears the entrance to the source room by epoch (C), but in epoch (D), it continues down the hallway. However, before it makes it too far, the waypoint drops in ranking sufficiently for it to turn around and reach the goal state in epoch (E).

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

We also explore aspects of the proposed RSS gradient tracking algorithm through the use of the EMCUBE ray-tracer [11] over a representative office layout shown in Fig. 8. This simulator provides a realistic model of RSS for an indoor space and allows for many tests of the same environment. This allows us to investigate how specific parameters affect the performance of the algorithm.

The simulated signal source transmits at 2.4 GHz. Because we are considering a fixed signal source, RSS is calculated off-line for each point on a grid with wavelength spacing, $\lambda = 12.5$ cm at 2.4 GHz.

Fig. 8. Map of simulated RSS for a typical indoor environment. Note that the EMCUBE simulation models complex multi-path phenomena.

In order to accelerate simulations, the robot is confined to move on the grid and looks up the RSS value for each location based on the offline EMCUBE calculations. So, we assume the propagation environment is fixed and the RSS values at the grid points will not change. It is further assumed that the robot will exactly calculate its position and the positions of obstacles. As a result, the path-distance to frontiers can always be accurately calculated and continuous evaluation of frontiers is precise. It is also assumed that the robot can explore every identified frontier and we set $k=8$ potential frontiers in our simulations (there are no out of bounds areas). An example of one simulation trial is depicted in Fig. 9.

The robot first explores its immediate surroundings (the upper hallway), to obtain a good RSS gradient estimate. Then it transitions to RSS frontier exploration. Its exploration leads it to sample the RSS in several rooms. Though it enters the rooms, it quickly decides to leave because the

Fig. 9. Physical environment with simulated test result trajectory

RSS gradient points back to the hallway, and the average RSS drops rapidly. The controller ultimately leads the robot to the signal source in the large lower room. Once the robot observes a sufficiently high average RSS, the goal condition is reached.

In order to further examine certain parameters, several tests were performed. The first involved changing the oscillation amplitude (i.e., amount of deviation from the straight path) of the robot as it tracked waypoints. The second involved removing the gradient and RSS average components to determine their effects on efficiency/capability of the controller.

A. Effect of Oscillation

We investigate how much the robot should deviate from the straight-line path as it moves towards each waypoint. Figure 10 shows the results of these tests. This plot shows the total distance traveled to reach the robot's goal condition as well as how often these path distances occurred for each oscillation amplitude.

In this set of simulations, a shorter total path distance indicates the robot was able to move towards the source without exploring a large portion of the environment. Longer total path distances indicate that a larger portion of the environment was sampled. The path can be extended by increasing oscillation amplitude or by exploring frontiers which do not lead to the signal source. As the oscillation increases from 0 to 0.375 m, the average distance traveled decreases. This improvement in efficiency is due to more accurate gradient estimates from spatially separated RSS measurements (see Section II). As the oscillation increases

Fig. 10. Traversed path length to source for different RSS spatial sampling oscillation amplitudes. Multi-trial data is depicted, where the width of each bar grows with the number of occurrences for that path length.

beyond 0.375 m, we see that the improved gradient estimates become offset by the increase in distance traveled.

B. Effects of RSS Gradient and RSS Average

Determining how the RSS gradient and average magnitude contribute to the efficiency of the control is the objective of this test. In Fig. 11, the algorithm is tested with an oscillation amplitude of 0.375 m while changing the method for choosing frontiers.

Fig. 11. (A) Test using both RSS gradient and average (B) Test using average only (C) Test using gradient only

This figure shows the results from three different tests with ten trials each. In the first test, the algorithm was tested using both RSS average magnitude and gradient information. In the two subsequent tests, either the gradient or the average magnitude was used along with the inverse distance to choose frontiers. These results show that while it is possible to rank frontiers with only RSS average magnitude or RSS gradients, better efficiency can be obtained by using both.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have developed and demonstrated a new algorithm that seeks a radio source in an indoor environment. Our approach

uses RSS gradient estimation to prioritize the frontier exploration options. Several metrics for RSS spatial sampling while approaching the signal source were developed and implemented. The resulting control algorithm is applicable to a wide variety of scenarios because it does not require knowledge of the propagation environment beyond basic fading assumptions and does not require a map a priori.

Interesting directions for further study include multiple agents, and moving sources. Collaborative agents could lead to increased exploration efficiency, and these agents can also exploit RSS amongst themselves to maintain connectivity. Similarly, adapting to a moving source leads to control algorithms that can be exploited to maintain or enhance connectivity in a mobile ad hoc network (MANET).

APPENDIX I RSS GRADIENT ESTIMATION

We assume that a mobile sensor makes RSS measurements Z_i at locations $(X_{i,1}, X_{i,2})$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. We center the locations so

$$\sum_i X_{i,1} = \sum_i X_{i,2} = 0. \quad (1)$$

We are interested in finding the gradient of the RSS measurements. We perform a 2-dimensional least-squares estimation, i.e., we fit a plane to the measurements. \mathbf{Z} is a random $n \times 1$ column vector and \mathbf{X} is a $n \times 2$ matrix. The gradient β is a 2×1 column vector that indicates the direction of steepest gradient ascent,

$$\mathbf{X}\beta = \mathbf{Z} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = (\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{Z}. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is the least-squares solution with 2 parameters with centered data [12]. This centering of the locations allows us to disregard any constant offset in the RSS measurements, because from (1) and (3) we see that

$$\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{X}^T (\mathbf{Z} + c\mathbf{1}^{n \times 1})$$

for some scalar c .

The estimated gradient direction and slope magnitude is

$$\hat{\theta}_S = \tan^{-1} \frac{\beta_2}{\beta_1} \quad (4)$$

$$|\beta| = \sqrt{\beta_1^2 + \beta_2^2}. \quad (5)$$

From (3) we observe that $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ must be non-singular for β to have a unique solution. The geometric interpretation is that the sampling locations must not be co-linear. We use singular value decomposition (SVD) to write $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{V}^T$ where \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V} are unitary and \mathbf{S} is diagonal. We note that $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ is symmetric and therefore its eigenvectors (columns of \mathbf{V}) are orthogonal. We can then rotate the coordinate system so that the eigenvectors are $\langle 1, 0 \rangle$ and $\langle 0, 1 \rangle$, i.e., $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{I}$ and so $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{S}$.

When $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ is non-singular, (3) can be written

$$\beta = (\mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{S})^{-1} (\mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{U}^T) \mathbf{Z} \quad (6)$$

$$= \mathbf{S}^+ \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{Z} \quad (7)$$

$$= \mathbf{X}^+ \mathbf{Z} \quad (8)$$

where $(\cdot)^+$ indicates pseudo-inverse, e.g., $\mathbf{X}^+ \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{I}$. The diagonal elements of \mathbf{S}^+ are the inverse root eigenvalues of $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$, i.e., $1/\sqrt{\lambda_1}, 1/\sqrt{\lambda_2}$.

APPENDIX II

EFFICIENT SAMPLING FOR RSS GRADIENT

Successful estimation of RSS gradient requires a strategy for sampling inside a physical environment. In particular, straight-line trajectories lead to degenerate gradient estimates, as discussed in Section I. We discuss how we perturb the paths in order to improve the accuracy of our gradient estimates.

The ranking of the frontiers relies on the accuracy of the RSS gradient estimate, which in turn depends on where the RSS measurements are taken. That is, the RSS sampling strategy strongly affects the reliability of the RSS gradient estimates β , which we quantify by its variance

$$\text{Var}[\beta_i] = \sum_j X_{i,j}^+ \text{Var}(Z_j) + \dots \\ \sum_{j,k>j} X_{i,j}^+ X_{i,k}^+ \text{Cov}(Z_j, Z_k). \quad (9)$$

For an idea of how the variance of the RSS gradient depends on \mathbf{X} , consider the situation where $\text{Var}[Z_i] = \text{Var}[Z]$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $\text{Cov}(Z_j, Z_k) = 0$ for $j \neq k$. It follows from (7) and (9) that

$$\text{Var}[\beta_i] = \sum_j X_{i,j}^+ \text{Var}(Z_j) = \sum_j S_i^2 U_{i,j}^2 \text{Var}(Z_j) \\ = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \text{Var}(Z) \sum_j U_{i,j}^2 = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \text{Var}(Z) \quad (10)$$

where λ_i is the i^{th} eigenvalue of $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$. Thus, the variance of the gradient decreases as the eigenvalues of the locations matrix \mathbf{X} increase. Geometrically, this guides us to consider sampling locations spread further apart rather than confined to a small region.

Fig. 12 plots $(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)/2$ for simple sampling strategies (regular polygon, square, rectangular spiral) for a fixed distance traveled. The regular polygon and square have comparatively large confidence because measurements are well separated spatially, but the spiral takes measurements in a more confined manner. We note that these strategies are approximately rotationally symmetric and so the eigenvalues in either direction are roughly equal. Thus, these strategies are well-suited for RSS gradient estimation in low-SNR regimes, where no prior gradient information is known.

When prior gradient estimates are available, a different sampling strategy can be employed to make more efficient movements. For example, suppose that the previous gradient estimate guides the movement in direction θ . Rather than traversing a regular polygon, a zig-zag or gently oscillating path in direction θ can be taken instead (see Fig. 4). Equation

Fig. 12. Eigenvalues of simple sampling strategies

(9) indicates that this directional strategy leads to high quality (lower variance) gradient estimates in the direction of travel θ , but low quality (higher variance) estimates perpendicular to θ . The disparity of the variance depends on how elongated the strategy is. If the movement is over a thin strip, confirmation of the RSS gradient will be reliable in the direction of travel, but the decision to change trajectory will be less reliable. Thus, unless we are extremely confident that θ is correct, we want the sampling strategy to have reasonable spatial separation in both dimensions.

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